

Table 1: Techniques, methodologies, methods, frameworks, tools, processes and/or tools identified in the SLR

Type	Proposal	References
Tools	Comparative analysis of the tools proposed in the existing literature on this topic	[1]
Frameworks	Minimum set of ethical requirements for artificial intelligence (AI) systems	[2]
	Application of the ECCOLA method in the context of co-operation in multi-robot systems	[3]
	A comprehensive field guide to the development of machine learning	[4]
	A framework for ethical evaluation utilising matrices	[5]
	A framework for organising software organisations according to different functional layers	[6]
	Framework for implementing AI ethics within a project-based learning environment	[7]
	Support sets for operationalising ethical AI principles	[8]
	Conceptual framework for the ethical cost of AI	[9]
	AI ethics framework is based on the Variables, Criteria, Indicators and Observables (VCIO) model	[10]
	Governance framework to identify and mitigate ethical problems	[11]
	Framework for calculating a system’s fairness	[12]
	Fairness in Design	[13]
	Ethics by Design framework utilising neural networks	[14]
	Ethical impact framework	[15]
Methodologies	Deployment model for the Eccola method	[16]
	Evaluation of ethical impacts of AI based on requirements engineering	[17]
	Hourglass model for organisational governance	[18]
Methods	Eccola	[19]
	Gaps in the Eccola method	[20]
	A analysis of the Eccola method in the context of the GARP framework	[21]
Processes	Value-Sensitive Design applied to AI	[22]
	Z-inspection	[23]
	Catalogue of process standards	[24]

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